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ABSTRACTS

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OP-009

Biosynthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles using *Simarouba glauca* leaf extract and screening for their antibacterial, antioxidant and anti-cancerous applications

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Abstract: The green synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles and their applications in biomedical field have gained huge attention in recent years due to their various physico-chemical properties. The present study 0.1mM of copper sulphate solutions is used as precursor to synthesis CuO NPs from *S. glauca* leaf extract, which was visually indicated by the color change from brown to green color and further calcinated at 200 °C for 2 h. The synthesized CuO NPs were characterized using X-ray crystallography (XRD) to detect the crystallinity of the particle and Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) indicated the rod-shaped structure of the CuO NPs. These were further screened for their biological properties like antibacterial, anti-angiogenic, antioxidant and anti-cancerous properties. CuO NPs showed great antibacterial activity for Gram-positive bacteria compared to Gram negative. The CuO NPs possessed antioxidant and angiogenic activity in dose dependent manner. The cytotoxicity effect of NPs was assed against HCT-116 and HeLa cell line, the IC₅₀ value was found to be 17.89±0.60 µg/ml and 20.21±0.33 µg/ml at 72 h. The anti-ROS property was assessed for both cell lines and the results were plotted using histogram.

Keywords: Copper oxide nanoparticles, *Simarouba glauca*, antioxidant, anti-angiogenic, anti-cancerous, anti-ROS.

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